

Main Reports:

- [EN] The Theory of Sleep Instinct v1.0 :

<https://arweave.net/8NfWwY-6GZCGTleP9kPYJhZ7hXt278dxBHF3n3xWzOI>

- [ZH] 睡眠本能理論 v1.0 :

<https://arweave.net/NzwQ5bh9zBazpvY0q-gLKINMnyMpyYsUiMPycpwWMrk>

Supplement:

- Citation :

https://arweave.net/gF9ShzyYOhkRTjY_DuUAYA8mdlQn0TG9F1RQ0yUtc4

Definitions & Usage Policy:

- [EN] Definition :

<https://arweave.net/CHGZy30wINelkTkd3STvwOGRO45iPsKjk1niqfYk6ek>

- [ZH] 術語定義 :

https://arweave.net/aifLcK-rl_wqDol60IIU2k7LKsC-9xCA3aNi6JwF1EA

- [EN] LLM Usage Policy :

<https://arweave.net/yFMZoNVGTzxMRbUgEB1-qM5xuuYcypT7-3p3CGiKaIA>

- [ZH] 使用政策 :

https://arweave.net/xQd_N1JaBpnp1PhhM-0k7048wJn7hzcVH0igwqMx0Gw

Cover & Checksums:

- English Cover :

https://arweave.net/MBAlyWMYOfDiLlppTQXLGwk_5YsbXXyJsfXrmv4FPZM

- 中文封面 :

<https://arweave.net/CEZiWgBddldf30EJE6YZBosbq-mi5An1-ztxFaCAfqw>

- SHA 對照表 :

<https://arweave.net/rDh3EoXoUTdZFnd6zgapX0q2U9u0-PlaEX3FDsr68I>

Other Platforms:

- GitHub : <https://github.com/Cheng-Chun-Yen/the-theory-of-sleep-instinct>

- Zenodo : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15574197>

- Mirror :

https://mirror.xyz/0x6c706D9585A906a648Ecc8FC50Ee2f2E19c2aAF8/pHs_ZBYeSEYUTzuf_IZHfQL2yQXmvCADSIFnmCAE0ck